

MICROBIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF BOTTLED WATER SOLD IN ABA METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT

Ten popularly sold bottle water in Aba metropolis was microbiologically analyzed, the samples were collected randomly from local markets, shops and street vendors within the Aba metropolis, Eastern Nigeria. Different microbial groups that were present in the water samples were also evaluated and results showed the presence of coliforms and indicator organism *Escherichia coli*. The water samples were analyzed and, the Microorganism obtain were identify and characterized. Physical parameters which include colour, odour, pH were also evaluated, results showed that the samples were all colourless, odourless, while the pH of the water samples were in the range of 6.31-7.45. The occurrence of the individual isolates showed that *Escherichia coli* had the highest occurrence 7(64%), followed by *enterobacter species* and *Klebsiella species* 6(55%), and followed by *staphylococcus species* and *proteus species* 5(46%), *bacillus subtilis* 3(27.3%), *bacillus species* and *chromobacter violaceum* had the least occurrence 2(18.2%). From the results, it was concluded that most bottled water sold in Aba metropolis contain coliform bacteria in the brands of bottled water product examined in this study. And the reasons could be attributed to non stringent compliance to Standard Operational Procedures (SOP) stipulated by the regulatory agency during the production of the bottled water products.

Keywords: local markets, Eastern Nigeria, street vendors, Aba metropolis, coliforms.

Introduction

Water is one of the most indispensable needs for the continued existence of all living things. Water supply and accessibility is goal 6 of the sustainable development goals (SDGs) and aims at ensuring environmental sustainability [1]. Satisfactory supply of clean, safe and hygienic drinking water is imperative for health and access to safe drinking water is a vital agent for human living. Water is needed in the body for digestion, translocation, absorption and excretion of metabolic wastes, secretion of hormones, enzymes and other biochemical body functions [2]. Nature is a great purifying system, water passes from the sky to the earth, from the earth to the streams, rivers, and to the sea, and then returns back to the sky [3]. But this natural process is breaking down in a global scale.

Bacterial Contaminants

Coliform bacteria in bottled water represent a great threat to public health, especially for infants, young children, and immunocompromised persons that could contact waterborne diseases, even at lower infectious doses. World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that potable water should have below 20 CFU/mL heterotrophic bacterial counts with no coliform bacteria, fecal coliforms, *E. coli*, enterococci, and *P. aeruginosa* (4). Coliform bacteria belong to *Enterobacteriaceae* family and include species of the following genera: *Citrobacter*, *Enterobacter*, *Escherichia*, *Hafnia*, *Klebsiella*, *Serratia*, and *Yersinia*. The presence of coliform microorganisms in drinking water represents a sign of fecal contamination and indicates the potential contamination also with pathogenic bacterial species such as *Shigella* spp., *Salmonella* spp., or *Vibrio cholerae*. They are used traditionally as indicators of water quality because the testing methodology is simple and inexpensive.

E. coli can survive in drinking water at 15–18°C for 4–12 weeks and does not multiply significant in the external environment. According to WHO (2006) *E. coli* are rarely found in water in the absence of fecal pollution, and no differentiation is made between pathogenic and nonpathogenic *E. coli* when this species is isolated from water. Therefore, water that contains *E. coli* is unsafe for consumption due to the strong association between *E. coli* and fecal contamination.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

The study area is Aba metropolis, Abia State, Nigeria. Aba is a commercial town in Abia-State, South-East Nigeria. The town lies on the longitude 30 East of Greenwich Meridian and latitude 25 north of the Equator. Aba has international recognition due to the presence of small scale industries and a number of local markets. In Aba, there is lack of pipe-borne water, improper water management and purification systems. Moreover, there is lack of proper environmental sanitation. Against this backdrop the commercialization of bottle water was implemented with the intention to supply portable and treated water to its inhabitants.

Sample Collection

This study was carried in April 2022 and a simple random sampling technique was used to select ten bottle water brands from the registered factories in Aba metropolis, and taken to the laboratory for analysis. The samples were coded A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, and J to reflect the respective brands. The bottle water samples were collected under aseptic condition and transferred to sterile universal containers.

Physical parameters

Physical analysis was carried out on the bottle water samples to determine the odour and general appearance. All the bottle water samples analyzed was clear, colorless, and odourless. The pH of water sample was also checked using a PH meter.

Work bench preparation

To avoid contamination the work bench was cleaned with cotton wool soaked in 70% alcohol. The clean, sterile containers were labelled appropriately. The different brands of bottle water were transferred into the labelled sterile containers.

Media preparation

The culture media used include Nutrient agar to determine the total viable bacterial count, Eosin Methylene blue (EMB) agar to enumerate *Escherichia coli*, MacConkey agar for coliform count and Salmonella-Shigella agar for the determination of salmonella and Shigella counts. Culture media were all prepared by the weighing out certain grams of the agar powder and dissolving in specific volume of distilled water according to the respective manufacturer's specification and sterilized in an autoclave at 121 at 15 psi for 15 minutes.

The autoclaved media were carefully poured into different Petri dishes. A sterility check was carried out, where the media was left for 24 hours inside the incubator. This is to ensure that the plates were sterile. The plate without growth in it was sterile and used to for the Sub-culturing.

Enumeration and isolation of bacteria

A 1 ml aliquot of each water sample was inoculated aseptically on each of the sterilized agar using the spread-plate method as described by Cheesbrough (2006). The plate was incubated for 24 hours at 37°C, after which visible colonies were counted and expressed in cfu/ml. Distinct colonies were selected and purified by repeated streaking on Nutrient agar, EMB agar, Macconkey agar plates respectively, (Onuigbo, 2023).

Principle of spread plates technique

The spread plate's technique involved using a sterilized L-shaped rod spreader with a smooth surface made of glass to apply a small amount of bacteria suspended in a solution over a plate. The plates need to be dry and at room temperature so that the agar can absorb the bacteria colonies evenly distributed on the plate.

Procedure of spread plate technique

Serial dilution of 10 was made from the water sample. Using a new, clean, sterile calibrated pipette, 0.1ml of water were dropped unto the prepared agar plate and evenly distributed using an L-shaped glass rod spread that has been dipped into the water and flamed over a Bunsen burner. The plates were incubated at 37 for hours. The colony forming unit (CFU) value of the sample was calculated. Once the colonies were counted, it was multiplied by the appropriate dilution factor to determine the number of CFU/ml in the original sample, (Onuigbo, 2023).

Characterization and identification of isolates

Bacteria

Bacteria were identified using differential stains, biochemical tests as described by Cheesbrough (2006) while characterization was used. A thin smear of the 24 hours culture was made on a clean grease free slide and heat fixed. It was flooded with crystal violet and allowed to stand for 1 minute. It was rinsed with slow running tap water then flooded again with grams iodine for 30 seconds. It was rinsed with water again then declorised with acetone for 5 seconds and again rinsed under

slow running tap water till no colour comes off. It was air dried and immersion oil was dropped, this was viewed under the 100 objective lens of the microscope.

BIOCHEMICAL TESTS CARRIED OUT

Catalase test:

This was done according to the methods described by Cheesbrough (2006). 2-3 drops of hydrogen peroxide was placed on a clean grease free slide, using a glass rod, colonied were taken from a 24hour old culture and dropped on the slide, bubbling within 5 seconds were recorded as positive.

Coagulase test:

The methods described by Cheesbrough (2006) were also adopted. Drops of serum were dropped onto a clean grease free slide and then a loopful of the organism was added, visible clumping within 5-10 seconds was recorded as positive.

Oxidase test:

This was done according to the methods described by Onyeagba (2004). A few drops 1% aqueous solution of tetramethyl-p-phenylene-diamine hydrochloride reagent was added to a piece of filter paper in a Petri dish smear of the bacteria were made onto the impregnated filter paper in a Petri dish using a glass rod. A purple coloration appearing within 5-10 seconds is a positive result.

Citrate test:

This is done as described Cheesbrough (2006). Simmons citrate agar was prepared according to the manufacturer's instruction in test tubes, they were allowed to gel. The tubes were inoculated by streaking the isolates using a sterile wire loop. It was then incubated at a colour change from green to blue indicated a positive test.

Indole test:

The method described by cheesbrough (2006). A loopful of the bacteria isolates was inoculated into sterile peptone water and incubated for 24 hours at 37 c, and then to this culture, 0.5ml of kovacs reagent (p-dimethyl amino benzaldehyde) was added and thoroughly mixed, this was allowed to stand. Presence of a deep colour was a positive result.

Urease test

This was prepared according to the methods described by Cheesbrough (2006). Christensen's urea agar prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions. It was dispensed in tubes, slanted and allowed to gel. The slope was then inoculated with the bacteria isolates using the streaking method; this was incubated at 37C for 24 hours. A positive test was indicated by a colour change from yellow to pink.

Methyl red test

This was done according to the method described by Cheesbrough (2006). 5mls of peptone water was dispensed into tube and a loop full of the bacteria isolate as inoculated into the medium. It was incubated at 37C for 3-5 days of the incubator, methyl red, was then added. A colour change indicative of a positive test, from yellow to red.

Vogues Proskeur test

This was done according to the method described by Cheesbrough (2006). 5mls of peptone water was dispensed into a tube and a loop full of the bacteria isolate as inoculated into the medium. It was then incubated at 37C for 3-5 days. Alpha naphthol; was added first then KOH was added. A red coloration showed a positive reaction.

Determination of activity of different antimicrobial agents against the isolates obtained from water samples:

Isolates from the water samples were tested for sensitivity against standard conventional antibiotic discs like, Cefotaxime (30µg), Cefuroxime (30µg), Gentamicin (10µg), Cefixime (5µg), Ofloxacin (5µg), Augmentin (30µg), Ciprofloxacin (5µg), and Nitrofurantoin (300µg), manufactured by Abtek Biological Ltd, England. A loop full growth of each isolate on nutrient agar was suspended in sterile distilled water, and was serially diluted in steps of ratio 1:10 to give turbidity equivalent to 0.5 MacFarland standard that is a density of 1×10^8 cells/ml before inoculation. Nutrient agar was inoculated with 0.5ml suspension of each isolate adjusted to 1×10^8 cell/ml, with the aid of sterile forceps sensitivity disc containing antibiotics were placed on the surface of each nutrient agar plate evenly seeded with test isolates and was incubated for 24 hours at 37C (Benson, 2005).

Statistical Analysis

Results were presented in tables and the frequencies of occurrence of the isolated bacteria were calculated using percentage for better clarification.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The bacteriological assessment of 10 popularly sold bottle water in Aba metropolis was evaluated in this study. Table 1 shows the physical parameters of the water samples, table two shows, the different microbial groups present in the water samples, table three shows the colony forming units of the bacteria on the water samples, table four shows the morphological and biochemical characterization of the isolates, and table five shows the occurrence of individual isolates.

Table 1: Physical parameters

WSC	COLOUR	ODOUR	pH
A	Colourless	Odourless	7.45
B	Colourless	Odourless	7.31
C	Colourless	Odourless	6.90
D	Colourless	Odourless	5.53
E	Colourless	Odourless	6.31
F	Colourless	Odourless	6.42
G	Colourless	Odourless	7.12
H	Colourless	Odourless	6.69
I	Colourless	Odourless	6.52
J	Colourless	Odourless	6.53

Table 2: Different microbial groups present in the water samples

WSC	THBC	TCC	TEC
A	+	+	+
B	+	+	+
C	+	-	-
D	-	+	+
E	+	+	+
F	+	-	-
G	+	+	+
H	+	+	+
I	+	+	+
J	+	+	+

Key: + = positive; _ = Negative' WSC – water sample code; THBC – total heterotrophic bacteria count; TCC –total coliform; TEC – total *Escherichia* count;

Table 3: Colony forming units of the bacteria on the water samples

WSC	COLOUR	ODOUR	pH
A	1.8	1.0	7.4
B	8.0	4.0	1.4
C	3.9	1.6	2.9
D	6.0	1.5	2.6
E	6.0	7.0	5.0
F	3.5	2.8	3.4
G	6.2	1.0	1.2
H	7.2	4.5	1.5
I	7.0	5.4	6.0
J	2.6	4.5	4.0

Key: WSC – water code; THBC; Total heterotrophic bacteria count; TCC – Total coliform; TEC – total *Escherichia coli* count; TNTC – too numerous to count.

Conclusion

In the past years, the consumption of bottled water is preferred to consumption of tap water, the public considering them to be sterile, uncontaminated due to the fact that these products are more processed, and somehow more controlled. But, the risk for health should not be minimized, taking into account the microbial metabolic diversity and versatility, making different species capable to survive, and even multiply in the conditions offered by bottled waters. On the other hand, the supplementary procedural steps (packaging, bottling, handling, transport) may sometimes increase the risk of microbial contamination of the final product. Therefore, the consumption of bottled waters is not free of any risks regarding microbial contamination and consequent water or foodborne disease, especially in countries where the legislation and control of these products are not strictly regulated and respected.

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